

CLIMATE CHANGE AND ENERGY TRANSITION IN THE GLOBAL ECONOMY: A LEGAL EXAMINATION OF THE SHIFT FROM OIL DEPENDENCY IN NIGERIA TO A DIVERSIFIED ENERGY MIX*

Abstract

Vast energy resources in the form of fossil fuels and gas to wit: a state may enrich itself with is both a blessing and a curse, and Nigeria has not been an exception to the applicability of this paradox. For decades, the oil industry has served as the backbone of Nigeria's economy, contributing over 80% of the national revenue and in the long run triggering an oil dependent syndrome. But, the contemporary global shift towards renewable energy, driven by the palavers of climate change and declining fossil fuel demand presents a gloomy future. This research aimed at examining Nigeria's legal efforts at transitioning from oil dependency to a diversified energy mix, within the broader legal framework of the global imperatives of energy transition and climate change. It adopts a doctrinal methodology, employing analytical and comparative approaches, while relying on primary sources such as statutes, international treaties, and judicial decisions, alongside secondary materials like textbooks, journals, and valuable reports. The study highlights the dual necessity of energy diversification: reducing reliance on fossil fuels while addressing Nigeria's contribution to climate change. Findings reveal that despite abundant renewable energy resources, Nigeria's economy remains undiversified due to infrastructural deficits, technological gaps, corruption, and weak implementation of viable policies. The research recommends strengthening legal and institutional mechanisms, enforcing climate change legislations, and fostering collaboration with international bodies to promote renewable energy investment and ensure Nigeria's alignment with global energy transition goals are achieved.

Keywords: Climate Change, Energy Transition, Oil Dependency, Renewable Energy, Diversified Energy Mix, Fossil Fuels.

1. Introduction:

Nigeria's oil and gas industry has been a major driver of economic growth since the discovery of crude oil in 1956 at Oloibiri, Bayelsa State. By 1960, the country entered the global energy market through the export of 847,000 tons of crude oil, marking the transition from an agrarian economy to one dominated by oil.¹ Today, with 15 operational pipelines and an average daily production of 1.5 million barrels as of 2023, Nigeria stands as the second largest oil producer in Africa and fifteenth globally.² As the backbone of the national economy, the oil and gas industry has generated immense revenue, accounting for about 5.5 percent of Nigeria's GDP, approximately 90 percent of foreign exchange earnings, and providing millions of jobs. In 2022 alone, the economy grew by 3.3 percent, with the World Bank projecting similar growth in 2024 and 2025.³ But, this economic growth is precarious and linear, as it rests heavily on oil dependency at a time when the global economy is moving away from fossil fuels. The global economy is advancing towards cleaner, low-carbon energy systems, which is spurred by the urgent need to address global warming and mitigate environmental crises. The Paris Agreement of 2015 for instance enjoins nations to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and accelerate the adoption of renewable energy.⁴ For oil dependent economies like Nigeria, this global energy transition poses two challenges; the first being a declining oil demand that threatens the stability of revenue,⁵ and the second being the country's continued reliance on fossil fuels which contributes to the climate change crisis.

Even if Nigeria has abundant petroleum resources, it can't also be disputed that Nigeria possesses vast renewable energy resources too, which includes solar, wind, hydropower, biomass, and geothermal energy sources distributed across different regions of the country. These resources could meet the energy demands of the nation and most importantly, improve access to increased electricity, yet power supply remains inadequate due to the entrenched reliance on fossil

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¹ G Etikerentse, *Nigerian petroleum law* (2nd edn, Lagos: Drew Publishers, 2004) p 10.

² P. Ukpe, 'Growth in Oil Sector' *This Day Life*. <<https://www.thisdaylive.com/index.php/2024/08/27/growth-in-oil-sector-gdp-contribution-shows-nnpc-strategies-wo-rkingby-ukpe-philip/?amp>> accessed 1 April 2025

³ D. Sasu, 'Oil Industry in Nigeria: Statistics and Facts' <<https://www.statista.com/topics/6914/oil-industry-in-nigeria/>> accessed 2 April 2025; Nigeria Bureau of Statistics (2023). Nigeria Gross Domestic Product Q4 2023. <<https://nigeriastat.gov.ng/eLibrary/read/1241460>> accessed 2 April 2025.

⁴ J Klein, 'The Paris Agreement and the Future of Climate Change Negotiations' (7 December 2020) *Stockholm environment institute* <<https://global.oup.com>> accessed 2 April 2025

⁵ T G Ikoli and N Chinery, 'Ending Nigeria's Oil Dependency: Not if, But When...and How' (9 March 2022) *Natural Resource Governance Institute*. <<https://resourcegovernance.org/articles/ending-nigerias-oil-dependency-not-if-whenand-how>> accessed 4 April 2025.

fuels, weak infrastructure, and policy inefficiencies.⁶In view of this, the natural resource wealth of Nigeria has often been described as a paradoxical ‘resource curse,’⁷that undermines sustainable development in the country and prevents the nation from advancing in the global energy market. This research examines the economic implications of Nigeria’s oil dependency and the legal framework shaping its energy sector. It further evaluates existing diversification initiatives while assessing their effectiveness in advancing a balanced energy mix in light of Nigeria’s Climate change commitments.

2. Conceptual Clarifications

Fossil Fuels

Fossil fuels are carbon-based energy resources formed over millions of years through the anaerobic decomposition of prehistoric plants and animals, originating from ancient photosynthesis. They are non-renewable by nature and are exhausted once extracted and consumed.⁸ The three major fossil fuels are coal, crude oil also known as petroleum, and natural gas, all of which has remained central to global industrialisation and economic development since the mid-18th century. Crude oil, commonly referred to as ‘oil’ or ‘petroleum,’ is a liquid hydrocarbon found beneath the surface of the earth, and is typically mixed with organic compounds and trace metals. Section 16 of the Petroleum Act⁹ defines crude oil as ‘oil in its natural state before it has been refined or treated, excluding water and other foreign substances.’ Once extracted, crude oil undergoes refining processes such as fractional distillation to produce a wide range of petroleum products including gasoline (petrol), diesel, aviation fuel, liquefied petroleum gas, lubricating oils, waxes, naphtha, bitumen, and asphalt.¹⁰ While fossil fuels have historically powered industrial growth, transportation, and electricity generation, they are the largest source of anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions contributing significantly to global warming and climate change. According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change Sixth Assessment Report in 2023, fossil fuels account for over 75% of global greenhouse gas emissions and nearly 90% of carbon dioxide emissions.¹¹ This heavy burden on the climate has made the continued reliance on fossil fuels across all economies a subject of legal, economic, and environmental debates.

Oil Economy

An oil economy is an economic system which is heavily dependent on the production and export of petroleum resources as the primary source of national income and revenue. In such economies, oil often dominates foreign exchange earnings and fiscal budgets, while also serving as a principal source of energy generation.¹² The concept can also refer to the oil sector itself, encompassing the upstream, midstream, and downstream activities in the country. Oil based economies are concentrated in regions with substantial reserves, e.g. Middle Eastern countries like Saudi Arabia, Iraq, Iran etc, Latin American countries like Venezuela and African countries like Nigeria and Angola.¹² In these countries, hydrocarbon exports constitute significant portions of the GDP and government revenues, making them equally vulnerable to global oil price volatility and shocks. For example, the 2014 -2016 oil price crash plunged several oil economies, including Nigeria and Venezuela into recession. Another problem of oil economies is the ‘resource curse’ theory, a paradox where wealth from resources fuels corruption, poor governance, and neglect of other productive sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, and technology. In Nigeria, for instance, oil constitutes about 90% of export earnings and more than half of government revenue, nonetheless the country continues to grapple with high poverty levels, poor infrastructure, and economic instability. The overreliance on oil alone also comes with environmental costs: as oil spills, gas flaring, and land degradation, especially in the Niger Delta, with its attendant human rights implications continue to tear through the country.

Energy Mix

The concept of energy mix refers to the proportion or amount of different primary sources of energy available and used within a country or region to meet the overall energy demand of a country. It encompasses fossil fuels, nuclear and renewable energy.¹³ Energy mix must be distinguished from power generation mix which relates specifically to electricity production. Energy mix includes and has broader applications such as in transportation, industrial use, and

⁶ V N Emodi, S D Yusuf and Kyun-Jin Boo, ‘The Necessity of the Development of Standards for Renewable Energy Technologies in Nigeria’ (2014) 5(11) 7-16 *Smart Grid and Renewable Energy Journal* <<http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/sgre.2014.511024>> accessed 5 April 2025

⁷ A Elwefelli and J Benhin, ‘Oil a Blessing or curse: A Comparative Assessment of Nigeria, Norway and the United Arab Emirates’ (2008) 8(5)*Theoretical Economics Letters*, <<http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/tel.2018.85076>> accessed 5 April 2025

⁸ H Onyi-Ogelle and D Nwosu, ‘Exploration and Production of Shale Oil as a Renewable Energy for Sustainable Development in Nigeria’ Need for Legal Alignment (2020) 2(2) 45 *International Journal of Comparative Law and Legal Philosophy* (IJOCLLEP)

⁹ Cap. P10, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004

¹⁰ Similar definition was provided in Petroleum Industry Act 2021, s 328

¹¹ IPCC, ‘AR6 Synthesis Reports’ <<https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/syr/>> accessed 2 September 2025 ¹²Global Studies Review, ‘Oil Based Economies’ <<https://library.fiveable.me/key-terms/hs-global-studies/oil-based-economies>> accessed 8 April 2025

¹² World Economic Forum, ‘Which economies are most reliant on oil’ <<https://www.weforum.org/stories/2016/05/which-economies-are-most-reliant-on-oil/>> accessed 8 April 2025

¹³ C Uzoma, E Nnaji and M Nnaji, ‘The Role of Energy Mix in Sustainable Development of Nigeria’ (2012) 5(1) 21-29 *Willoud Journals*

residential consumption.¹⁴ Globally, fossil fuels continue to dominate energy supply. According to the International Energy Agency (IEA) World Energy Outlook 2019, coal, oil, and gas together constituted about 84% of global primary energy consumption, while hydropower was around 6.8%, other renewables around 4%, and nuclear energy lagged far behind at about 4.4%.¹⁵ However, the transition towards a cleaner energy mix is also accelerating and gaining momentum, renewable energy for instance accounted for nearly 30% of global electricity generation in 2022, which is driven by policy measures, falling technology costs, and climate change commitments amongst states.¹⁶ In Nigeria, the energy mix remains skewed and unsustainable. As of 2018, the total amount of energy people use were from traditional biomass and waste being about 73%, fossil fuels around 26%, hydropower around 0.5 to 1%, and other renewables around 0.5%.¹⁷ This heavy reliance on biomass reflects the widespread energy poverty in Nigeria, where millions of households lack access to modern electricity and clean cooking fuels. Meanwhile, the fossil fuel dependency limits the ability of Nigeria to meet its climate obligations under the Nationally Determined Contributions submitted to the UNFCCC. Reforming the Nigerian energy mix is important not only to improve access to energy and ensure energy security but also to align Nigeria with its international decarbonisation commitments.

Renewable Energy

Renewable energy also known as clean or green energy refers to energy derived from natural processes that are continually replenished on a human timescale, such as sunlight, wind, water flow, geothermal heat, and biological processes.¹⁸ Unlike fossil fuels, which are finite and carbon intensive, renewable energy cannot be exhausted, and it generates less greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, which is important for climate change mitigation and sustainable development. Okposin¹⁹ describes renewable energy sources as those 'that can be replaced on a human timescale, with minimal or no negative environmental consequences, and whose utilization does not result in depletion of the earth's surface.' However, renewable energy is not always synonymous with 'low carbon energy' since nuclear energy, for example, is low carbon but not renewable. But nevertheless, renewable energy is more evenly distributed across the world than fossil fuels, which reduces the geopolitical risks of energy dependency. In fact, its deployment across electricity, heating, cooling, and transport sectors is considered a cornerstone of the global energy transition.²⁰ The adoption of renewable energy sources by countries aligns with the global climate agenda under the Paris Agreement of 2015, which requires nations to rapidly scale up low carbon and renewable energy systems in order to limit global temperature rise to well below 2°C, and ideally 1.5°C, above pre-industrial levels.²¹ For Nigeria, renewable energy is more than a technical option, it is a legal imperative and an important policy put into action. The Climate Change Act 2021 requires Nigeria to pursue net-zero emissions by 2060, while the National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy of 2015 also seeks to integrate solar, wind, hydropower, biomass, and other renewables into the national energy mix. Failure to do so in practical terms does not only scupper the climate commitments of Nigeria but it inadvertently also perpetuates the existing energy poverty, where over 85 million Nigerians lack access to electricity.²² Major renewable energy sources include:

Solar Energy: Solar energy is the most abundant renewable resource. It is derived from the radiation of the sun and is harnessed through technologies such as photovoltaic panels and concentrated solar power systems. The earth is said to receive about 10,000 times more solar energy annually than global energy demand, which makes it a limitless resource for the world.²³ For Nigeria, a country that is located near the equator with average daily sunshine of 5.5 kWh/m², solar energy is greatly promising for rural electrification and decentralised power generation. Projects such as the Solar Power Naija programme targeting 5 million households demonstrate the potential of solar energy in Nigeria to reduce reliance on diesel generators and expand access to cleaner energy.²⁴

Wind Energy: Wind energy is a form of renewable energy source that converts the kinetic energy of air currents into electricity through turbines, either onshore that are land-based or offshore that are sea-based. Offshore wind holds higher

¹⁴ A Bongers, 'Energy Mix, Technological Change and the Environment' (2022) 24, 341-364 *Environmental Economics and Policy Studies* <<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10018-021-00324-8>> accessed 8 April 2025

¹⁵ IEA, 'World Energy Outlook 2019' <<https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-outlook-2019>> accessed 2 September 2025

¹⁶ Ibid

¹⁷ International Energy Agency, 'Nigeria's Energy Outlook' <<https://www.iea.org/articles/nigeria-energy-outlook>> accessed on 9 April 2025.

¹⁸ K R Ullah *et al*, 'A review of solar thermal refrigeration and cooling methods' *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* (2013) 24(1) <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2013.03.024>> accessed 10 April 2025

¹⁹ A Okposin 'Assessing Policy and Legal Framework Challenges in Renewable Energy Development in Nigeria', (2019) 6(2) 103-116 *Journal of Public Policy in Africa*

²⁰ Ibid

²¹ United Nations Climate Change, 'The Paris Agreement, What is the Paris Agreement' <<https://unfccc.int/process-and-meetings/the-paris-agreement>> accessed 2 September 2025

²² WorldBank Group, 'Nigeria to Expand Access to Clean Energy for 17.5 Million People' <<https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/press-release/2023/12/15/nigeria-to-expand-access-to-clean-energy-for-17-5-million-people>> accessed 2 September 2025

²³ H Ajaelu and R Okereke, 'Assessment of Nigerian Renewable Energy Potentials and Energy Poverty: Challenges and Prospects' <<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16552.03842>> accessed 9 April 2025

²⁴ Rural Electrification Energy, 'Solar Power Energy' <<https://spn.rea.gov.ng/>> accessed 2 September 2025

potential due to stronger and more consistent wind speeds, though it requires higher initial investment.²⁵ The energy from the wind strongly depends on the wind speed in the location where the wind energy conversion system is to be sited. Though average wind speeds vary considerably by location, the technical potential of the world for wind energy exceeds global electricity production and large potential exists in most regions of the world to enable significant wind energy deployment.²⁶ Many parts of the world have strong wind speeds, but the best locations for generating wind power are sometimes remote ones, however, regions in the northern and southern latitudes have the highest potential for wind power.²⁷

Geothermal Energy: Geothermal energy is a type of energy that is derived from heat stored beneath the earth's crust. It is usually tapped through hydrothermal reservoirs or enhanced geothermal systems. Unlike solar and wind energy, geothermal is not dependent on weather conditions, which makes it a stable renewable resource.²⁸

Hydropower Energy: Hydropower or hydroelectric power harnesses the energy of water moving from higher to lower levels. It can be generated from reservoirs and rivers and is one of the largest forms of renewable energy. Reservoir hydropower plants rely on stored water in a reservoir, while run-of-river hydropower plants harness energy from the available flow of the river.²⁹ Hydropower reservoirs often have multiple uses such as providing drinking water, water for irrigation, flood and drought control, navigation services, as well as energy supply. Hydropower currently is the largest source of renewable energy in the electricity sector. It relies generally on stable rainfall patterns and can be negatively impacted by climate-induced droughts or changes to ecosystems which in turn affect rainfall patterns. Compared to other energy sources, hydropower also has relatively low costs throughout the duration of a project lifetime in terms of maintenance and operations.³⁰

Bioenergy: Bioenergy is a renewable energy stove from organic matter such as wood, agricultural residues, manure, and dedicated energy crops. It can be used directly which is known as biomass combustion or processed into biofuels like ethanol, biodiesel and biogas. Although bioenergy offers opportunities where waste is converted to energy, its large-scale use is problematic in view of sustainability; Deforestation, change in land-use and food security trade-offs are often major risks. In Nigeria, biomass still accounts for nearly 73% of the primary energy mix, mainly for cooking and heating, which is an unsustainable reliance that contributes to deforestation and indoor air pollution that have severe health implications.³¹

3. The Resource-Curse Theory and The Nigerian Oil Dependency:

The Resource curse theory also known as 'the paradox of plenty' or 'the poverty paradox' is the hypothesis that countries with an abundance of natural resources such as fossil fuel and other minerals, have lower economic growth and poorer development outcomes than countries with fewer natural resources.³² In 1993 Richard Auty first used the term 'resource curse' to describe how countries rich in mineral resources were unable to use that wealth to boost their economies and how these countries had lower economic growth than countries without an abundance of natural resources.³³ The Resource curse makes mineral-rich countries experience the 'Dutch-disease' when they become overly dependent on a single primary commodity(oil) export, leading to adverse effects on the exchange rates and productivity in other sectors. The abundance of natural resources may also shift factors of production away from the industries with increasing returns to scale.³⁴ Weak linkages between the oil industry and the rest of the economy lead to significant and persistent unemployment rates, while broad-based development and growth do not occur. This, in turn, creates even more poverty, stifles development and leaves the country trapped in a resource curse. Countries that fall under this category include amongst others, Venezuela, Iran, Iraq, Kuwait, Qatar, Congo and Nigeria.³⁵ Nigeria being the African Nation most

²⁵ International Renewable Energy Agency, 'Wind Energy' <<https://www.irena.org/Energy-Transition/Technology/Wind-energy>> accessed 9 April 2025

²⁶ A Siddiqi, S Khan and S Rehman, 'Wind Speed Simulation Using Wavelets' (2005) 2(2), 557-564. *American Journal of Applied Sciences* <<https://doi.org/10.3844/ajassp.2005.557.564>> accessed 9 April 2025.

²⁷ A Kumar, M Khan and B Pandey, 'Wind Energy: A Review Paper' (2018), 4(2) 29-27 *Gyancity Journal of Engineering and Technology* <<https://doi.org/10.21058/gjet.2018.42004>> accessed 10 April 2025

²⁸ R Bertani, 'Geothermal Power Generation in the World 2010-2014 Update Report' 60(1) 31-43 *Geothermics* <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geothermics.2015.11.003>> accessed 10 April 2025

²⁹ United States Department of Energy, 'Hydropower Basics' <<https://www.energy.gov/eere/water/hydropower-basics>> accessed 9 April 2025.

³⁰ *Ibid.*

³¹ A Giwa *et al.*, 'A Comprehensive Review on Biomass and Solar Energy for Sustainable Energy Generation in Nigeria' (2017) 69, 620-641 *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.11.160>> accessed 9 April 2025

³² M Ross 'The Political Economy of the Resource Curse' (1999) 51 (2) 297-322 *World Politics* <<http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/S0043887100008200>> accessed 7 April 2025

³³ *Ibid.*

³⁴ A Savoia and K Sen, 'The Political Economy of the Resource Curse: A Development Perspective' (2021) *Annual Review of Resource Economics* <<https://doi.10.1146/annurev-resource-100820092612>> accessed 10 April 2025

³⁵ F V Ploeg, 'Natural Resource: curse or Blessing?' (2010), 49(2) 366-420 *Journal of Economic Literature* <<http://dx.doi.org/10.1257/jei.49.2.366>> accessed 10 April 2025

endowed with resources is still bedeviled by poor economic development and energy insufficiency, providing a vivid example of a country affected by the resource curse.

4. Statutory Framework of Energy Diversification in Nigeria

Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999

The 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria places the regulation of the energy sector on both the Exclusive and Concurrent Legislative Lists. The Federal Government exclusively regulates oil and gas as well as nuclear energy, while both the Federal and State governments jointly regulate electricity generation, transmission, and distribution. Paragraphs 39 and 41, Part II of the second Schedule to the constitution empower the National Assembly to make laws on oil and gas and nuclear energy, respectively. Similarly, Paragraph 13 empowers the National Assembly to legislate on electricity for the Federation, while Paragraph 14 empowers State Houses of Assembly to legislate on electricity within their respective States. Although the CFRN does not expressly mention renewable energy, signalling a significant lacuna, it can be interpreted purposefully that Paragraphs 13 and 14 extend to electricity generated from both non-renewable and renewable sources. Secondly, Chapter II of the constitution, even if non-justiciable, contains provisions that directly affect environmental protection and sustainability, which are core issues relating to climate change. Section 20 imposes a duty on the State to ‘protect and improve the environment and safeguard the water, air and land, forest and wildlife of Nigeria.’ Similarly, Sections 16(2)(d) and 17(2)(d) envisage a national economic policy directed towards environmental sustainability and the preservation of human dignity. The overwhelming dependence of Nigeria on oil and gas, which are primary drivers of greenhouse gas emissions, is antithetical to these constitutional aspirations. The continued prioritisation of fossil fuel exploitation without a concrete transition plan derogates from the spirit of Section 20, as emissions from oil extraction and gas flaring affect air quality, contaminate land and water, and contribute to the global climate change crisis. While these important constitutional provisions are primarily non-justiciable, they nevertheless set out a binding directive principle of state policy, providing a constitutional framework that morally requires Nigeria to pursue a diversified and environmentally sustainable energy mix.

Petroleum Industry Act 2021

The Petroleum Industry Act of 2021 (PIA) is the principal law for the oil and gas sector in Nigeria. It repealed various laws regulating the petroleum sector. The PIA provided for two regulatory agencies; the Nigerian Upstream Petroleum Regulatory Commission and the Nigerian Midstream and Downstream Petroleum Regulatory Authority. As regards renewable energy sources, section 64(h) of the PIA provides that the NNPC Limited is to engage in the business of renewables and other energy investments. It is therefore implied from the above provisions that the NNPC Limited can indulge in renewable energy projects in competition with private investors, which is aimed at the development of alternative energy resources in Nigeria. Secondly, the PIA contains important provisions on gas flaring and environmental protection, which are critical to the discussion of climate change. Section 104 prohibits routine gas flaring or venting, and only permits the same in cases of emergency, for safety reasons, or with the written approval of the Commission. When flaring occurs without lawful authorization, under the Act, companies are liable to pay prescribed penalties, and such payments are not to be treated as a license to flare. This provision can well be said to reflect the commitment of Nigeria on paper to reducing greenhouse gas emissions, although practical enforcement has historically been weak, and Nigeria remains one of the highest gas flaring nations in the world. Furthermore, the Act establishes a Host Communities Development Trust under sections 235 to 257, requiring oil companies to set aside 3% of their operating expenditure for the benefit of host communities. This provision is intended to provide funds for environmental remediation, infrastructure, and social welfare in host communities that have borne the brunt of environmental degradation. Similarly, the Midstream and Downstream Gas Infrastructure Fund, created under section 52, aims to promote gas-based industrialization and further domestic gas utilization, which could serve as a transitional energy pathway to lower emissions compared to crude oil. In view of Nigeria’s heavy reliance on oil and gas: a dependence that both negatively affects energy transition and exacerbates environmental harm, the PIA represents a paradox. On one hand, it creates essential provisions that at least on paper, advance diversification, environmental accountability, and community development. On the other hand, less attention is paid to renewable energy, and the enforceability of anti-flaring is not water-tight.

Electricity Act 2023

The Electricity Act was signed into law by President Bola Ahmed Tinubu, GCFR, on June 8, 2023. The Act repealed existing laws, including the Electric Power Sector Reform Act of 2005.³⁶ And it seeks to reposition the Nigerian electricity sector within the purview of the global energy transition. It emphasizes the integration of renewable energy into Nigeria’s energy mix, aligning national energy policy with international commitments on climate change and sustainability goals. The Act harmonizes the rules governing the Nigerian Electricity Supply Industry with the intention of restructuring the electricity sector and accelerating the development of renewable energy sources. Section 1 establishes a framework for boosting renewable energy, attracting investment, improving electricity access, and

³⁶ The Act also repealed the Hydroelectric power producing areas Development commission Act 2010 and also the Nigerian Electricity Management Service Agency Act 2015

promoting indigenous technological capacity.³⁷ Section 34 of the Act³⁹ requires the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission to promote renewable energy development as a central regulatory objective under the Act. The Act also provides for embedded generation, hybridized generation, and electricity production from renewable sources.³⁸ Section 164 of the Act³⁹ further directs the Commission to actively support the development and utilization of renewable energy, prescribing measures to increase its contribution to Nigeria's energy mix. The Supreme Court, in the landmark case of *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch v Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation*,⁴⁰ also hinted that both nationally and internationally, stronger measures are being adopted to safeguard the environment for the benefit of present and future generations.

Energy Commission of Nigeria Act 1979

The Energy Commission of Nigeria Act was first promulgated in 1979 and later amended in 1988 and 1989. By virtue of the Act, the Energy Commission of Nigeria (ECN) was established and saddled with the responsibility of coordinating and exercising general surveillance over the systematic development of Nigeria's various energy sources.⁴¹ The Act also created the Technical Advisory Committee of the ECN, which is empowered to advise both the state and federal government on energy development issues, including the funding of energy research and development. In addition, the Committee is obliged to liaise with international organizations in energy matters such as the International Atomic Energy Agency, the World Energy Conference, and other similar global institutions.⁴² The ECNA demonstrates an early recognition of the need for energy diversification in Nigeria. Section 1 of the Act lays out the departmental structure of the commission, which includes units responsible for energy efficiency, rural energy development, and alternative and renewable energy sources. This indicates that, even at its inception, the Commission was designed not only to oversee the traditional energy sector but also to build institutional capacity for integrating renewable energy and promoting conservation, objectives that are now critical to the global energy transition agenda today. In contemporary times, the relevance of the ECNA has become even more pronounced. Nigeria, as a party to the Paris Agreement, has pledged to reduce its greenhouse gas emissions and achieve net-zero by 2060. The ECN is a critical driver in advancing this commitment. For instance, at the Brazil Energy Summit 2025, the DG of the Commission unveiled the Nigerian Energy and Emissions Calculator 2060, a tool designed to serve as the primary instrument for assessing and planning Nigeria's energy systems, focusing on energy demand and supply dynamics, greenhouse gas emissions, and the integration of evidence-based policies to support national development goals.⁴³

Environmental Impact Assessment Act 2004

The Environmental Impact Assessment Act (EIAA) establishes the general principles, guidelines, and procedures for assessing the environmental consequences of proposed projects in Nigeria. Its application extends to both renewable and non-renewable energy projects, ensuring that potential environmental and social impacts are evaluated and mitigated before the project is implemented. By integrating environmental accountability into project planning, the Act can also be said to reflect Nigeria's effort to balance development with sustainability. Section 2 of the Act requires power developers planning energy projects to register with the Federal Ministry of Environment for the conduct of an Environmental Impact Assessment. This provision ensures that projects likely to have significant environmental consequences undergo a rigorous review process before approval. It also compels developers to integrate sustainability considerations into their planning and design, thus aligning Nigeria's development agenda with international environmental governance standards. The EIAA is also reinforced by the 2017 Environmental Impact Assessment Guidelines, which provides detailed procedures for conducting assessments. More specifically, power generation projects must submit their EIA reports to the Federal Ministry of Environment and obtain the requisite approvals before commencement. The objective is to prevent or minimize negative environmental outcomes associated with energy and power generation activities, such as deforestation, biodiversity loss, greenhouse gas emissions, and community displacement.

Climate Change Act 2021

The climate change Act of 2021 is a highly important statute, as it integrates responses to climate change within Nigeria's legal system. It was enacted in November 2021, and it operationalizes Nigeria's pledge under the Paris Agreement, especially its net-zero emissions target by 2060. Section 1 of the Act sets up a comprehensive framework for achieving low greenhouse gas emissions, inclusive green growth, and sustainable development. It requires: The formulation of long-term mitigation and adaptation programmes, the coordination of climate actions aligned with national development, mobilization of resources and integration of climate policy into larger socio-economic plans. The Act applies to all federal Ministries, Departments, Agencies (MDA's), public and private entities, ensuring that climate action is not relegated to environmental bodies alone, but is integrated across all governance structures in the country.

³⁷ *Ibid*

³⁹ *Ibid*

³⁸ E A, s 128(f)(i)-(vi)

³⁹ *Ibid*

⁴⁰ (2019) 5NWLR (pt 16666) 518

⁴¹ ECNA, Cap. E10 LFN 2010, s 1(1)

⁴² ECNA, s 5

⁴³ Energy Commission of Nigeria, 'DG ECN Highlights Nigeria's Sustainable Energy Vision at Brazil Energy Summit 2025'

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At the core of its institutional framework is the National Council on Climate Change (NCCC), which is chaired by the President. The NCCC is responsible for approving the National Climate Change Action Plan, administering the Climate Change Fund, and developing climate regulation tools such as carbon tax and emissions trading. Supporting it is a Secretariat tasked with technical, administrative, and monitoring functions, including data collection from stakeholders. Under Sections 15 to 19, The Act sets up a dedicated fund and Carbon-Budget to support climate action initiatives. The funds will be financed through: Appropriations by the National Assembly, International grants and resources, Revenues from carbon tax and emissions trading, Fines imposed on non-compliant entities and other sources as may be identified by the Council. The funds can be allocated toward administration, climate advocacy, mitigation/adaptation projects, support for vulnerable communities, and incentives for reducing emissions. A key innovation of the Act is the requirement for a carbon budget to maintain national emissions within temperature targets of 1.5 -2 °C above pre-industrial levels. The budget is subject to periodic revision and requires the approval of the Federal Executive Council. Complementing this is the five year National Climate Change Action Plan under section 20 of the Act, The plan addresses adaptation and mitigation activities, climate proofing of infrastructure, energy efficiency and conservation, renewable energy deployment, and alignment with global climate objectives. The Act under sections 22 to 24 also requires climate responsibilities across sectors, for instance, existing MDAs must integrate climate desks into their core functions and meet annual carbon reduction targets. Non-compliance can carry sanctions or fines. Private entities with 50 or more employees must also implement emission reduction strategies, appoint Climate Change Officers, and report annually.

5. National Policies on Energy Diversification

National Energy Policy 2003

The National Energy Policy (NEP) is the first ever comprehensive energy policy in Nigeria established by the Energy Commission of Nigeria in April 2003 to serve as a road map to a better national energy future. Prior to the approval of the NEP by the Federal Government of Nigeria, there was no comprehensive energy policy for the country. The policy covers key energy sectors; energy related issues such as environment, energy efficiency, energy financing and energy policy implementation. It includes strategies for systematic exploitation of energy resources, the development and effective use of energy manpower, supply of rural energy needs, efficient energy technology development and deployment, energy security and private sector participation.⁴⁴The main goal of the NEP is to create energy security through a robust energy supply mix by diversifying the energy supply based on the principle of ‘an energy economy in which the modern renewable energy increases its share of energy consumed and provides affordable access to energy throughout Nigeria, thus contributing to sustainable development and energy conservation.’⁴⁵

National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy 2015

The National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy was developed and drafted by the Energy Commission of Nigeria and was endorsed as a policy document on April 20, 2015 by the Federal Executive Council, to address the inadequacies of the previous energy policies, and drive renewable energy development and improved energy efficiency in Nigeria.⁴⁶The policy provides various financial and fiscal incentives for promoting renewable energy. These incentives include custom duty exemptions on imported equipment and materials used in renewable energy production, soft loans and low interest loans specifically dedicated to supporting renewable energy projects. This financial support facilitates access to affordable financing for renewable energy initiatives.⁴⁷ The overall objective of this policy is to ensure the development of the nation’s energy resources, with diversified energy resource option, for the achievement of national energy security and efficient energy delivery system with an optimal energy resource mix amongst other things⁴⁸

Nigerian Biofuel Policy and Incentives 2007

The Nigerian Biofuel Policy and Incentives (NBPI) was approved by the Federal Executive Council on 20th June 2007 in line with the Presidential directive issued to the defunct Nigeria National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) on an Automotive Biomass Program for Nigeria. The goal of the NBPI is the gradual reduction of the Nation’s dependence on imported gasoline and to develop the domestic fuel ethanol industry through the utilization of agricultural products.⁴⁹ The input of the policy as to renewable energy development includes the establishment of a Bio-fuel Commission, Issuance of a bio-fuel regulation by the Minister of Petroleum Resources, establishment of a biofuel research agency,

⁴⁴See National Energy Policy (NEP) (2003), Energy Commission of Nigeria (ECN), Abuja; Federal Republic of Nigeria, <www.energy.gov.ng> accessed 11 April 2025.

⁴⁵*Ibid.*

⁴⁶ National Renewable Energy and Efficiency Policy for Nigeria 2015, <www.energy.gov.ng> accessed 11 April 2025

⁴⁷National Renewable Energy Efficiency Policy 2015 <<http://www.power.gov.ng/download/NREEPPOLICY2015-FECapprovedcopy.pdf>>accessed 11 April 2025

⁴⁸*Ibid.*

⁴⁹ N V Emodi and N E Ebele, ‘Policies Enhancing Renewable Energy Development and Implications for Nigeria’ (2016) 4 (1) 7-16 *Sustainable Energy* <<http://pubs.sciepub.com/rse/4/1/2>> accessed 12 April 2025 ⁵²NNPC ‘Draft Nigerian biofuel policy and incentives’ National Biofuel and Incentives 2007. <<http://www.community.irena.org/rbsvc25562/attachments/rbsv25562/News/97/2/NationalBiofuelsPolicy.pdf>> accessed 12 April 2025

funding of research and development in bio-fuels development. This policy through the NNPC has succeeded in promoting the production of bio-fuels such as biodiesel and fuel-ethanol to be blended with Premium Motor Spirit (PMS) or petrol which has boosted economic development and reduced fossil fuel related greenhouse gas emissions in the transport sector.⁵²

6. International Frameworks on Energy Diversification and Climate Change:

United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change 1992:

The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change was adopted in New York on 9 May 1992 and entered into force on 21 March 1994. It has a near universal participation, with 198 Parties as of 2022, making it the foundational international legal instrument on climate change. The objective of the convention, as stated in Article 2, is the stabilization of greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere at a level that prevents dangerous anthropogenic interference with the climate system. This stabilization must occur within a timeframe that enables ecosystems to adapt naturally, safeguards food production, and permits sustainable economic development.⁵⁰ The Convention embodies the principle of common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities recognizing that while all states share the responsibility of combating climate change, developed countries bear a greater duty due to their historical contributions to global emissions. This principle is particularly relevant to the Global South, as it legitimizes the demand for financial support, capacity building, and technology transfer from developed countries.⁵¹ Institutionally, the supreme decision making body of the Convention is the Conference of the Parties (COP), which meets annually to assess progress and negotiate new commitments. Subsidiary bodies, such as the Subsidiary Body for Scientific and Technological Advice and the Subsidiary Body for Implementation, ensure continuous technical and policy development. Parties are required under Articles 4 and 12 to submit periodic national communications and Green House Gas inventories, which creates a framework for accountability and transparency. In relation to the Global South, provisions of the convention offer both opportunities and challenges. While the Convention sets out financial obligations for developed countries through the establishment of mechanisms like the Global Environment Facility, implementation has often been hampered by insufficient financing and slow technology transfer. For Africa and other developing regions, this creates a significant gap between commitments and practical realities. But the Convention laid the groundwork for subsequent protocols and agreements, including the Kyoto Protocol of 1997 and the Paris Agreement of 2015, by creating a global climate governance structure that brings together science, policy, and international cooperation.

The Paris Agreement 2015

The Paris Agreement, adopted on the 12th of December 2015 at COP-21 in Paris, also represents a significant evolution of the United Nations Framework on climate change. Entering into force on 4 November 2016, the Agreement builds on the existing United Nations Framework on Climate change while it also introduced forward-looking mechanisms to address climate change. Its primary objective, as provided in Article 2, is to hold the increase in global average temperature to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels, while pursuing efforts to limit it to 1.5°C.⁵² A key innovation of the Paris Agreement is the system of Nationally Determined Contributions under Article 4. Unlike the top-down model in the Kyoto Protocol, the Paris Agreement adopts a bottom-up approach that requires each Party to define its own commitments in line with national circumstances. Nationally Determined Contributions must be updated every five years, with each successive submission expected to represent a progression in ambition. This approach allows flexibility but has also been criticized for lacking the requisite enforcement mechanisms, which has led to concerns about the adequacy of global commitments. The Agreement also places emphasis on adaptation under Article 7 and climate finance under Article 9. Developed countries are enjoined to provide financial resources to assist developing country Parties with both mitigation and adaptation efforts. And the Agreement reiterates the goal of mobilizing 100 billion dollars annually by 2020, with a commitment to scale up thereafter. For the Global South, this provision is central, as adaptation rather than mitigation is often the immediate priority. For instance, small island states and African countries require urgent investments in coastal defenses, resilient agriculture, and disaster risk management. The Paris Agreement is both a legal and moral recognition of the urgent need for collective climate action. But its reliance on voluntary, nationally driven contributions creates a kind of uncertainty regarding whether the ambitious temperature goals can realistically be met. For the Global South, the Agreement is a legal foundation to demand climate justice, but its practicality depends heavily on political will, international solidarity, and the fulfillment of financial commitments by the Global North.

7. General Implications of Oil Dependency

Economic Implications of Nigeria's Oil Dependency: Over the years, it has been observed that the continued dominance of oil exports subjected the Nigerian economy to external shocks. Oil price shocks are sudden price

⁵⁰Wikipedia.org, 'United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change' <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/United_Nations_Framework_Convention_on_Climate_Change?utm=> accessed 2 September 2025

⁵¹ T Wang & S Gao, 'Reflection and operationalization of the common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities principle in the transparency framework under the international climate change regime' *Advances in Climate Change Research*, <<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1674927818301230>> accessed 2 September 2025

⁵² PA, Article 2(1)(a)

fluctuations resulting from changes in either the demand or supply in the international oil market. In Nigeria, oil price is a major determining factor of government revenue and expenditure, foreign exchange availability and the output. Consequently, fiscal management becomes complicated resulting in economic instability.⁵³ A crash in world oil market prices results in a drastic reduction in the foreign exchange inflow into the economy, it weakens the external reserves, and leads to further depreciation of the naira. It also causes increased cost of production, increased inflation rate and low standard of living in the long run.

Environmental Hazards Implications of Oil Dependency: The activities of the oil industry have resulted in serious environmental hazards, especially in the oil producing areas of the Niger Delta. Things like oil spillage, gas flaring and waste disposal has caused land degradation, deforestation, ecosystem degradation, air pollution and water pollution.⁵⁴ These environmental problems are detrimental to health, ecological balance and majorly agricultural and economic activities. Between 1979 and 1997, there were 5,334 reported cases of crude oil spillages, releasing around 2.8 million barrels of oil into the land, swamp, estuaries and coastal waters of Nigeria.⁵⁵ These environmental damages make it imperative for the Nigerian government to embrace renewable energy sources which are cleaner and do not cause environmental hazards.

The implications of Neglect and Non-Exploitation of Solid Minerals Resources: Nigeria is home to about 90 types of solid minerals and there are over 450 solid mineral occurrences which are located in different parts of the country. Examples of solid minerals found in Nigeria include amongst others, lead, uranium, limestone, iron ore, rock salt, gemstones like sapphire, beryl, emerald, precious metals like gold and diamond. The exploration and exports of these solid minerals were of great economic benefits to the country. Except for only a few cases, the commercial exploitation and export of solid minerals in Nigeria had long ceased with Nigeria's dependence on crude oil exports. For example, in the years 2013 to 2016, solid minerals contribution to the GDP was poor and almost entirely insignificant due to the country's over reliance on oil exports.⁵⁶

8. Harnessing Renewable Energy Potentials for a Sustainable Energy Future in Nigeria

In order to successfully transcend from oil dependency to a diversified mix for a sustainable energy future, it is imperative for Nigeria to harness its abundant renewable energy potentials scattered across various parts of the country. Carbon footprints can be reduced if the potentials are appropriately utilized and converted into accessible and affordable energy sources. The major renewable energy potentials in Nigeria are as follows;

Solar Energy Potentials

Nigeria has a landmass of about 924 Km² with an average irradiance per unit area of 5.535 KWh/m² and an average incident solar energy of 1831.06 KW/h annually. The sunshine hours in the country range from 9 hours in the far north to 3.5 hours in the southern part of the country.⁵⁷ With an average of 6 hours per day of sunlight, Nigeria receives about 4.85 x 10¹² KW/h of the sun's energy (3.8 x 10²³ KW/s) per day, equivalent to the energy derived from about 1.082 million tons of oil per day. This shows that a considerable amount of energy can be generated and utilized from the massive solar radiation available to combat the epileptic energy supply, leading to an absence of economic development.⁵⁸ There are various ways of exploiting solar energy in Nigeria, including solar photovoltaic cells for rural electrification; cookers, crop dryers, water pumps, heaters among others, can harness power from the sun. A fully operational solar PV manufacturing plant has been set up in Abuja by the National Agency for Science and Engineering Infrastructure, with a current capacity of 7.5 MW of power generation per year.⁵⁹ In Delta state, the government signed a Memorandum of Understanding with Yutal Li Nigeria Limited in 2016 to construct a 100 MW solar power plant in order to promote clean energy and the growth of micro, small and medium scale enterprises.⁶⁰ Other minor solar projects in Nigeria include the street lighting in Ekiti state, 7.2 KW Kwakwalawa village electrification in Sokoto State and 1.87 KW Iheakpu-Awka Village electrification in Enugu State, 1.5 tonne Solar Forage Dryer, Yauri, Kebbi State, amongst

⁵³ U Ekpo, 'An Analysis of the Economic Consequences of Nigeria's Dependence on Crude Oil Exports' (2022) 10 (6) 48-65 *International Journal of Development and Economic Sustainability* <<https://doi.org/10.37745/ijdes.13/vol10n64865>> accessed 9 May 2025

⁵⁴ See case of *Gbenre v Shell petroleum Development Company* (2005) 6 AHRLR 151 FHC/B/CS/53/05 30

⁵⁵ C Ugochukwu and J Ertel, 'Negative Impacts of Oil Exploration on Biodiversity Management in the Niger Delta Area of Nigeria' (2008) 26(2) 139-147 *Science and Education Publishing* <<https://doi.org/10.3152/146155108X316397A>> accessed 9 May 2025

⁵⁶ Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin (December 2017) vol 28 <<https://www.cbn.gov.ng>> accessed 10 May 2025

⁵⁷ D Abdullahi et al, 'Key Barriers to the Implementation of Solar energy in Nigeria: A Critical Analysis' (2017) 83 (1) 012015 *Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* <<https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/83/1/012015>> accessed 14 May 2025

⁵⁸ E Agbo et al, 'Solar Energy: A Panacea for the Electricity Generation Crisis in Nigeria' (2021) 7(5) e07016 *Heliyon* <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e07016>> accessed 14 May 2025

⁵⁹ G Ozoegwu and C Mgbemene and P Ozor, 'The Status of Solar Energy Integration and Policy in Nigeria' (2017) 70, 457-471 *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.11.224>> accessed 14 May 2025.

⁶⁰ *Ibid*

others.⁶¹ The vast expanse of the Sahel Savannah in the Northern region of Nigeria provides more than enough land space for solar energy projects to provide a substantial amount of energy for the country if properly harnessed.⁶²

Wind Energy Potentials

Wind energy potentials in Nigeria have over the years been tied to the northern parts of the country. Nigeria has an average wind speed of 3.0 m/s with a wind speed that ranges from 3.88m/s to 9.39 m/s in the North-West part of the country, 1.77 m/s to 4.5 m/s in the South-West, 2.46 m/s to 5.36 m/s in the North-Central and 3.30 m/s to 4.65 m/s in the South-South.⁶³ Wind speeds are generally weak in the southern part of the country except for the coastal regions and offshore location. Studies show that total exploitable wind energy reserve at 10m height may vary from 8 MWh/yr in Yola to 51MWh/yr in the mountainous areas of Jos Plateau and it is as high as 97 MWh/yr. in Sokoto. It also gives a potential estimate for 10 selected sites in the country to be between 3.6 m/s to 5.4 m/s.⁶⁴ Regardless of the viability of wind energy in Nigeria, the generation of power from wind is still developing in the country as no wind farms are contributing to the national grid. Small-scale wind turbines have been designed and used for purposes in the country such as water pumping, battery charging, small-scale enterprise electrification and experiments. The only large-scale onshore wind turbine in the country is located in the Rimi Local Government Area of Katsina state, with an estimated output capacity of 10 MW.⁶⁵ Small-scale wind turbines that exist in the country include the 5 KW wind energy system installed in Sokoto and the 1 KW wind power turbines installed in Bauchi Kedada and Katsina Goronyo for pumping water. The tremendous potentials and generation capabilities that could be harnessed from wind energy have not been fully utilized and gross energy yield is in its initial stage. Nigeria is thus yet to explore its wind energy resources, improving the standard of living for its citizens, especially those in the rural regions.⁶⁶

Hydro Power Potentials

The potential of hydropower energy in Nigeria is high and accounts for well over 38.5% of the country's total electricity power supply between 1999 and 2004. Yet only about 1930 MW, which constitutes 14% of the total exploitable hydropower in the country, has been utilized, contributing over 30% to the installed capacity connected to the grid. The country's total hydropower is 14,750 MW with 11,250 MW in Large hydropower and small hydro with a 3,500 MW share. Hydropower is the most utilized power resource for electric power generation and supply as the country's wealth of large rivers and waterfalls has been adequately leveraged.⁶⁷ Nigeria has two major hydropower stations with one located at the Kainji Dam with an installed capacity of 160 MW and the other at the Jebba dam approximately 82 km downstream of the former on the river Niger installed capacity of 96.4 MW. Other rivers in the country with energy generation potential include those in Rivers State, Kaduna, Benue and Cross River state, which could produce a total capacity of about 4650 MW. In comparison, the river Mambila can also generate about 2330 MW.⁶⁸ Though Nigeria uses major rivers for hydro energy generation, there is still the potential to utilize smaller rivers as small hydro schemes to meet energy demands of various rural communities either as a single electric power source or in combination with other renewable energy sources as a hybrid electric power source. The inherent advantage of small hydropower systems includes low magnitude on the environment and potential for flood prevention, navigation and irrigation which offers a sustainable means for meeting the needs of the rural dwellers as well as curbing the energy poverty in Nigeria.⁶⁹

Bio Energy Potentials

Nigeria is rich in bio energy and bio mass resources, including wood, forage materials and shrubs such as agricultural waste and by-products from local and industrial actions. The overall biomass and bioenergy potential in Nigeria is

⁶¹ O Awogbemi and C Komolafe, 'Potential for Sustainable Renewable Energy Development in Nigeria' (2011) 12 (1) 161-169 *The Pacific Journal of Science and Technology* <<http://www.akamaiuniversity.us/PJST.htm>> accessed 14 May 2025

⁶² T Olaoye et al, 'Energy Crises in Nigeria: Need for Renewable Energy Mix' (2016) 4 (1) 1-8 *American Journal of Electrical and Electronic Engineering* <<https://doi.org/10.12691/ajeee-4-1-1>> accessed 14 May 2025

⁶³ A Oluleye and Z Adeyewa, 'Wind Energy Density in Nigeria as Estimated from the ERA Interim Reanalyzed Data Set' (2016) 17 (1) 1-17 *British Journal of Applied Science and Technology* <<https://doi.org/10.9734/BJAST/2016/13340>> accessed 14 May 2025

⁶⁴ A Idris et al, 'Nigeria's Wind Energy Potentials: The Path to a Diversified Electricity Generation-Mix' (2012) 2(4). -2437 *International Journal of Modern Engineering Research (IJMER)* <https://www.ijmer.com/papersVol2_Issue4/CM2424342437.pdf> accessed 14 May 2025

⁶⁵ Y Mohammed et al, 'Existing and Recommended Renewable and Sustainable Energy Development in Nigeria based on Autonomous Energy and Microgrid Technology' 75 820-838 *Renewable and Sustainable Energy* <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.11.062>> accessed 15 May 2025

⁶⁶ W Ebhota and P Tabakov, 'The Place of Small Hydropower Electrification Scheme in Socioeconomic Stimulations of Nigeria' (2018) 13 (4) 311-319 *International Journal of Low-Carbon Technologies* <<https://doi.org/10.1093/ijlct/cty038>> accessed 15 May 2025

⁶⁷ I Omezia et al, 'Assessment of Performance of Turbo-Alternators at the Jebba Hydroelectric Power Station in Nigeria from 2005 to 2014' (2019) 38(1) 131-141 *Nigerian Journal of Technology (NIJOTECH)* <<https://dx.doi.org/10.4314/njt.v38i1.18>> accessed 15 May 2025

⁶⁸ K Okedu, R Uhumwangho and M Odje, 'Harnessing the Potential of Small Hydro power in Cross River State of Southern Nigeria' (2020) 37 (100617) 1-11 *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments* <<https://www.doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2019.100617>> accessed 15 May 2025.

⁶⁹ I Adejumbi and D Shobayo, 'Optimal Selection of Hydraulic Turbines for Small Hydro Electric Power Generation -A Case Study of Opeki River, South Western Nigeria' (2015) 34 (3) 530-537 *Nigerian Journal of Technology (NIJOTECH)* <<https://dx.doi.org/10.4314/njt.v34i3.15>> accessed 14 May 2025

estimated to be about 200 billion kg/year and 2.58 billion GJ (61.67 Mtoe) respectively, representing about 51% of total energy consumption in 2015. With an energy content of 6.0×10^9 MJ, Nigeria exploits 80 million m³ (4791.7kg) of fuelwood yearly for cooking, amongst other domestic purposes. Out of this energy content, only about 5% to 12% are currently used for domestic purposes, especially cooking.⁷⁰ The entire primary fuelwood and charcoal energy consumption were put at 32-40% between 1989 and 2000 and the country's national demand was estimated at 39 million tons for the year 2000. Household cooking and cassava processing were responsible for 95% of total fuelwood consumption.⁷¹ Over the years, biomass availability in Nigeria has been cut down, partly due to the demand for timber in the construction and furniture industries. An estimated 200 million tons of dry mass is obtainable from forage, grasses and shrubs, producing a total of 2.28×10^6 MJ of energy.⁷² Most people living in rural regions depend mainly on wood for shelter and fuel for burning, leading up to an annual loss of approximately 350,000 hectares of forest and vegetation by far lower afforestation rate of 50,000 hectares per year. The Megawatt-biomass gas turbine project in Ebonyi State is a modern example of biomass exploitation in the country that utilizes the husks of plants to generate energy in its contribution to the fast development of the state. The 5 MW to be developed will provide energy of about 2 MW to the mills and the Oferekpe waters will use 1.5 MW with the balance going to adjoining communities.⁷³ Nigeria can utilize plant biomass as fuel for small scale industries which could be fermented by anaerobic bacteria to produce a cheap fuel gas (biogases). Biogas production from municipal waste, agricultural residues and industrial waste does not compete for land, water and fertilizers with crops like is the case with bioethanol and biodiesel production. This will also reduce dangers posed by these wastes. Nigeria produces about 227,500 tons of fresh animal waste daily, since 1 kg of fresh animal waste produces about 0.03mbiogas,³ then Nigeria can potentially produce about 6.8 million of biogas every day from animal waste only.⁷⁴

Geothermal Energy Potentials

Nigeria has high geothermal energy potentials but the required technology is in the developing stage. It requires drilling deep down into rocks and earth's crust to gain access to the heat under the earth crust. Offshore drilling is common in the exploration of crude oil or fossil fuel in Nigeria's oil rich Niger delta region. Geothermal power was after wide researches found to be cost effective, reliable, sustainable and environmentally friendly, but has historically been limited to areas near tectonic plate boundaries.⁷⁵ Geothermal power is potentially viable in many cities in the country. From the record of geothermal gradient, it shows that many sites in Nigeria are good for geothermal system which is subject to confirmation with geophysical methods. As reported by Avbovbo, the geothermal gradients of the earth are between 2-3°C/100m and geothermal gradient above this range is considered to be a good site for geothermal system. the geothermal gradient of Niger Delta region of Nigeria ranges from 1.3 to 5.5°C/100m. the geothermal gradient of Anambra Basin ranges from 2.5 to 4.9°C/100m.⁷⁶ A similar study of the geothermal gradient of Bida Basin shows that it ranges from 2 to 2.5°C/100m. The Borno Basin temperature gradient ranges from 1.1 to 5.9°C/100m. the study of Sokoto Basin has revealed its geothermal gradient to range from 0.9 to 7.6°C/100m. The hot and warm springs are another indicator that shows the possibility of a geothermal system in Nigeria. The following areas have springs that indicate the leakage of geothermal systems from the crust; Akiri in Benue State with a hot spring of about 53.5°C, Wikki in Yankari Game Reserve among others which shows the feasibility of 50 MW geothermal power in Nigeria.⁷⁷

9. Standpoints in other Jurisdictions

United States of America (USA)

The USA is one of the top crude oil producers in the world, outproducing Nigeria by nearly nine times, yet oil constitutes less than 1% of its GDP reflecting a highly diversified economy where oil is one of many revenue streams. Unlike Nigeria, The U.S has leveraged its oil boom to become a net energy exporter, while policy incentives like the Inflation Reduction Act of 2022 have driven significant investments in renewables, with solar and wind experiencing cost reductions of 89% and 69%, respectively from 2010 to 2022.⁷⁸ USA also presents a more advanced stage of energy

⁷⁰ S Oyedepo, 'On Energy for Sustainable Development in Nigeria' (2012) 16(5) 2583-2598 *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* <<https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2012.02.010>> accessed 16 May 2025

⁷¹ *Ibid.*

⁷² *Ibid.*

⁷³ J Nyika et al, 'The Potential of Biomass in Africa and the Debate on its Carbon Neutrality' (2020) <<https://www.intechopen.com/online-first/the-potential-of-biomass-in-africa-and-the-debate-on-its-carbon-neutrality> > accessed 16 May 2025

⁷⁴ J Akinbami, 'Renewable Energy Resources and Technologies in Nigeria: Present Situation, Future Prospects and Policy Framework' (2001) 6(2) 155-182 *Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change* <<https://www.doi.org/10.1023/A:1011387516838>> accessed 16 May 2025

⁷⁵ T Olaoye et al, 'Energy Crises in Nigeria: Need for Renewable Energy Mix' (2016) 4 (1) 1-8 *American Journal of Electrical and Electronic Engineering* <<https://www.doi.org/10.12691/ajee4-1-1>> accessed 16 May 2025

⁷⁶ A Avbovbo, 'Geothermal Gradients in the Southern Nigerian Basin' (1978) 26, 268-274 *Bulletin of Canadian Petroleum Geology*, <<https://www.doi.org/10.35767/gscpgbull.26.2.268>> accessed 16 May 2025

⁷⁷ K Ewa and K Schoeneich, 'Geothermal Exploration in Nigeria' *Proceedings of World Geothermal Congress Bali, Indonesia (2010) Science and Education Publishing* <<https://www.sciepub.com/reference/143726>> accessed 16 May 2025

⁷⁸ U.S Department of Energy, 'Inflation Reduction Act of 2022' <<https://www.energy.gov/lpo/inflation-reduction-act-2022>> accessed 3 June 2025

diversification and renewable energy development, characterized by comprehensive legal framework and policies, as well as diverse sources and significant technological advancements far ahead of Nigeria. Wind energy, in particular, has seen remarkable growth in recent years.⁷⁹ The 2017 Wind Technologies Market Report by Wiser and Bolinger, highlights the USA's leadership in wind energy with sustainable investments in wind power infrastructure and technology. The report notes that wind energy now accounts for a significant portion of the country's total electricity generation, with continued growth expected due to technological improvements and declining costs.⁸⁰ The USA's approach to energy diversification is characterized by a combination of federal and state policies, including tax incentives, renewable energy development initiatives. For example, the U.S Energy Policy Act of 2005 in prioritizing renewable energy, propelled the production of electric cars and renewable energy driven plants, which is in contrast to Nigeria's Electricity Act which struggles with practical co-ordination, efficiency and translation.⁸¹

South Africa

South Africa's economy is less dependent on oil and its energy infrastructure is more developed than Nigeria's and it operates under a more diversified legal framework, with policies supporting both fossil fuels and renewable energy. The Renewable Energy Independent Power Producer Procurement Programme launched in 2011, has been a cornerstone of South Africa's diversification strategy, attracting over \$20 billion in private investment and adding 6.4 GW of renewable capacity by 2023, thus, driving renewable energy growth, with solar and wind projects increasing electricity access across the country.⁸² Also, the Integrated Resource Plan of 2019 outlines a balanced energy mix, targeting increased renewable and nuclear capacity while phasing out coal.⁸³ It provides a clear road map for energy transition and aligns with Paris Agreement commitments, unlike Nigeria's Petroleum industry Act which is oil oriented with limited provisions for renewable energy. The National Energy Regulator of South Africa (NERSA) regulates electricity pricing, enhancing energy access and renewable energy adoption which has been more efficient than Nigeria's National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy which has since its inception lacked solid mechanics for implementation. In the past decade, South Africa's renewable energy sector has witnessed massive development. The available renewable capacity is estimated to increase from 8 GW In 2017 to about 12 GW in 2023, representing a 40% growth rate. The Solar P.V. represents practically 50% of all the increments (1.6 GW) followed intently by inland wind (1.4 GW), CSP (0.4 GW), and bioenergy (0.2 GW). The country has a high installed capacity of hydropower with an estimated potential of 41,000 Megawatts, placing the country in a higher pedestal than Nigeria in the African energy landscape.⁸⁴

Nigeria's shift from oil dependency to a diversified energy mix is critical for sustainable development but it lags behind the USA and South Africa due to infrastructural, financial, and governance challenges. The USA's advanced diversification, driven by policy and innovation, offers a perfect model for Nigeria, while South Africa's progress through private investment and renewable programs also provides regional insights. To accelerate its transition, Nigeria must strengthen its legal frameworks, enhance policy implementation, attract foreign investment, and leverage its abundant renewable resources all within it.

10. Conclusion

Nigeria's overdependence on crude oil for revenue and energy has proven to be economically unsustainable and environmentally harmful, especially as the global community advances toward renewable and low-carbon alternatives. Although the country is richly endowed with renewable resources such as solar, wind, hydropower, and biomass, these resources remain underutilized due to weak enforcement of existing laws, institutional overlaps, corruption, and inadequate investment. To address this, Nigeria must strengthen its legal and institutional frameworks by establishing a unified regulatory body with clear mandates for diversification and renewable energy adoption. Incentives such as tax breaks, import duty waivers, and concessional financing should be deployed to attract private sector investment, while local content policies must promote indigenous expertise and technology transfer. Anti-corruption measures are also critical to dismantle vested oil-sector interests that usually obstruct progress. Furthermore, government support should extend to research and development in renewable technologies, rural electrification through off-grid solutions, and nationwide awareness campaigns to build public acceptance. International collaboration and climate finance mechanisms can also provide technical and financial support, while Nigeria's energy transition policies must remain aligned with its global commitments like the Paris Agreement and the 2060 net-zero target. By implementing these measures, Nigeria can reduce its vulnerability to oil shocks, advance climate sustainability, and secure a more resilient energy future.

⁷⁹ *Ibid*

⁸⁰ R Wiser and M Bolinger, '2017 Wind Technological Market Report' Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory <<https://doi.org/10.2172/1561894>> accessed 3 June 2025

⁸¹ I Idoko et al, 'Renewable Energy Policies: A Comparative Analysis of Nigeria and the USA' (2024) 21 (1) 888-913 *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews* <<https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.21.1.0071>> accessed 4 June 2025

⁸² O Akinbami, S Oke and M Bodunrin, 'The state of renewable energy development in South Africa: An overview' (2021) 60 (6) 5077- 5093 *Alexandria Engineering Journal* <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aej.2021.03.065>> accessed 10 June 2025

⁸³ South Africa-Energy <<https://www.trade.gov/country-commercial-guides/south-africa-energy>> accessed 10 June 2025

⁸⁴ U Justin et al, 'A Systematic Review on the Renewable Energy Development, Policies and Challenges in Nigeria with an International Perspective and Public Opinions' (2022) 11(1) 287-308 *International Journal of Renewable Energy Development* <<https://doi.org/10.147/ijred.2022.40359>> accessed 10 June 2025